

DIPLOMA

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RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

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**THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF E-COMMERCE IN THE CONTEXT OF THE
DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES**

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